

Instruments for Assessing the Quality of the Air

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Abstract

Straightforward reading Rapid decision-making is made possible by the information provided by air quality devices or monitors at the moment of sampling. When using this equipment, a skilled and knowledgeable user can ascertain whether site workers are exposed to airborne concentrations of certain hazardous air pollutants that beyond the limits of immediate exposure. Air quality monitors can be helpful in recognizing radioactive risks, combustible atmospheres, increased amounts of airborne pollutants, and oxygen-deficient or oxygen-enriched atmospheres that are instantly threatening to life or health. When it comes to locating emissions like gas leaks or point-source pollution, direct reading instruments are especially helpful. It is frequently essential to periodically check airborne levels using a real-time monitor, particularly before and during job activities. When conducting screening surveys, direct-reading devices are helpful in identifying areas that require further investigation.

Keywords: Impacts, Instruments, Air Quality, Environments, Air Pollution, Safety, Disadvantages.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the main issues facing the environment worldwide is air pollution. The World Health Organization [1] reports that population morbidity overall is higher in cities with more polluted air. Due to its detrimental effects on human health and even mortality, particulate matter, particularly tiny particles (PM_{2.5}) with a diameter of 2.5 micrometers or less, is considered one of the most dangerous elements of urban emissions [2–5]. The current scenario is made worse by the positive association that exists between air pollution and the COVID-19 virus's spread. The cornerstone for the virus's long-distance spread is particulate matter (PM). Additionally, PM exacerbates COVID-19 patients' symptoms. In 2020, these data will be published in numerous international papers [6–8]. While PM concentrations decreased significantly during the quarantine period, as demonstrated by Daniella and Leonardo Rodriguez-Urrego [9], air quality monitoring continues to be the most significant activity for scientists worldwide, including those in Ukraine [10]. It is common knowledge that the air we breathe is contaminated. Pollution comes from a variety of sources, particularly in large cities. A number of sensors are in place to keep an eye on air pollution. The Air Quality Index (AQI) is one of the international measures used to track the number of contaminants in urban air. Ground-level ozone, particle pollution, carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide, and nitrogen dioxide are the five main air pollutants that are measured by air quality sensors. These data are then combined to create the Air Quality Index. Additionally, even though the sensors can't lower air pollution on their own, you can still make suggestive maps of urban pollution using the data they offer [12].

II. RELATED WORKS

Air quality knowledge depends on measurements of the lower atmosphere's vertical structure. Drones, or unmanned aerial systems, can measure temperature, pressure, and relative humidity reliably and at a minimal cost. On a UAS, a set

of low-cost sensors managed by an Arduino microprocessor board were compared to a meteorological-grade sensor. A forward-moving sampler and a vertical ascension sampler were the two sampling modalities investigated. Vertical aerosol distributions during an inversion event might be retrieved with the integration of a tiny particle sensor (Sensiron SPS30). The temperature probe based on thermocouples and the Bosch BME280 sensor's relative humidity measurement showed strong correlations with the meteorological sensor. Then, on a platform that made a rocket-like sound, the temperature and relative humidity sensors were installed. The rocket sounding mechanism worked effectively up to 400 meters in altitude. It was discovered that the low-cost sensors functioned well enough for low-cost development and application in research and teachings [13]. This paper provides an innovative approach to air quality prediction and examines how it relates to various urban activities and environmental conditions, including traffic density. In order to accomplish this goal, we integrate traffic density from closed-circuit television footage and real-time data from several environmental sensors into a multi-modal framework that we propose. Within a streaming dataset, the framework efficiently handles data discrepancies caused by malfunctioning cameras and sensors. The dataset displays complicated real-world features such as outliers, noise interference, and sudden camera or station activations or deactivations. By applying a particle swarm optimization (PSO)-based merit fusion of the sensor data to train a joint model on data from adjacent stations and sensors, the proposed approach addresses the problem of predicting air quality at places without sensors or with malfunctioning sensors. Several LSTM model variants, such as bi-directional LSTM, CNN-LSTM, and convolutional LSTM (ConvLSTM), are used to test the suggested technique. The results show an improvement over the ARIMA model of 48%, 67%, and 173% for short-, medium-, and long-term periods, respectively. The quantity of airborne particulate matter (PM) in the ferroalloy sector can be rather high, which is concerning for both the environment and occupational health. In recent years, there has been interest in small, inexpensive sensors that measure PM, which allow for extensive monitoring of PM levels in the environment. These sensors haven't, however, been thoroughly tested in environments comparable to the metallurgical industry's indoor spaces. By comparing the low-cost, commercial Nova PM SDS011 particle sensor in two distinct ferroalloy plants, this study seeks to close this gap. The Fidas 200S, which has undergone suitable testing and certification in compliance with the most recent EU regulations (EN 15267, EN 16450), was used as the benchmark. A silicomanganese alloy (SiMn) plant tested twelve Nova sensors over the course of three months, while a silicon (Si) plant tested thirty-five sensors in a single month. The findings demonstrated that while the low-cost Nova sensors reported lower dust concentrations than the Fidas 200S, they had all the same trends and peaks in terms of PM concentration. The higher measurement range of the Fidas, measuring down to 180 nm compared to the Nova, which measures down to 300 nm, and the size and mass percentages of particles in Si dust compared to SiMn dust are the reasons for the larger discrepancy, which was expected, at the silicon plant. The data from the Nova sensors was found to be useful for comparing dust levels over time for various operations, at various locations, and under various operating conditions, notwithstanding the differences in absolute numbers [14]. Historically, costly measurement apparatus has been used in a small number of permanent locations to conduct conventional air quality monitoring. When hot spots are absent, for example, the resulting sparse spatial air quality data does not accurately reflect the actual air quality of the entire region. This project focused on creating an affordable network of cloud-based air quality measuring systems in order to acquire air quality data with improved spatial and temporal resolution. These platforms ought to be capable of measuring the following factors related to air quality: air temperature, relative humidity, gases like NO, NO₂, O₃, and CO, and particle matter (PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and PM₁). On average, these parameters were recorded every minute and sent to a cloud server every second. The platform created for this study processed, read, and stored sensor data in the cloud using a single main computer. Three prototypes were put to the test in real-world settings: two in the busy Marienplatz traffic site in Stuttgart, and one at a remote location in Ötisheim where measurements were taken close to active railroad tracks. The designed platform proved to be reliable during the measurement phase and had material costs for one air quality sensor node of about 1500 euros. It was also investigated whether a dryer could function more effectively by using a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller, which would lessen the adverse impact of climatic factors like air temperature and relative humidity on the measurement outcomes. This is thought to be one method of raising the caliber of data that inexpensive sensors are able to collect [15]. Whether indoors or out, preserving human health and well-being depends on monitoring air quality (AQ). Particulate matter (PM) is one of the most important metrics that needs to be checked on a regular basis. Poor spatial and temporal AQ information results from the high cost and difficulty of deploying traditional reference particulate analyzers on a broad scale. But it's still unclear how accurate and dependable these sensors are. The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effectiveness of five inexpensive sensors for air quality (AQ) monitoring in compliance with US EPA recommendations by contrasting them with a particle reference analyzer. SLR models, or basic linear regression, were used to assess the sensors in both indoor and outdoor conditions. The findings show that inexpensive sensors cannot be relied upon to measure air quality correctly indoors. During the three-week analysis period, for a 1-hour average, the coefficient of determination (R²) values ranged from 0.2 to 0.58, indicating a weak correlation between the sensors and the reference analyzer. With an R² value of 0.72, the sensor (HPMA115) did, however, meet the US EPA-recommended standard after increasing the average time interval. Certain sensors' root-mean-square error (RMSE) values were higher than the US EPA's recommended threshold of less than 7 µg/m³ for PM sensors. Temperature, indoor relative humidity (RH), and PM_{2.5} concentration were found to have possible influences on sensor behavior. Variations in RH and temperature were noted between testing with and without occupants, indicating that the air conditioning system also had an impact on the sensor's function. The outcomes

demonstrated that inexpensive sensors, like Honeywell's HPMA115, may be used in outdoor settings. But the calibration procedure needs to be carried out for every unique environment. Our research revealed the shortcomings of inexpensive sensors for air quality monitoring and the necessity of additional study to create trustworthy sensors [16, 17]. Urban air pollution is a major problem that necessitates effective air quality management to maintain acceptable health levels. By expanding the spatial distribution of ambient air quality monitoring—a task that can be accomplished with inexpensive sensors—the hotspots can be found. It is widely acknowledged that numerous factors impact their outcomes, nevertheless. High relative humidity can significantly affect the quality of data obtained from low-cost Particulate Matter (PM) sensors. To mitigate the effects of elevated relative humidity on the outcomes derived from inexpensive PM sensors, a low-cost dryer was created and its efficacy was examined. A test chamber was developed for this purpose, and professional reference devices and inexpensive PM sensors were added. The test chamber's relative humidity was controlled via a vaporizer. Depending on the voltage, the inexpensive dryer heated the sample air to a manually controlled temperature. To determine the ideal voltage with the lowest energy usage and the highest drying efficiency, several voltages were evaluated. We evaluated the inexpensive PM sensors with and without the inexpensive dryer. The outcomes of the experiment confirmed that the low-cost dryer's use lessened the impact of relative humidity on the low-cost PM sensor readings [18].

III. IMPORTANT BENEFITS OF AIR QUALITY MONITORING

The following are some significant advantages of monitoring air quality.

1. We are able to evaluate the effects of poor air quality on public health thanks to the data gathered from air quality monitoring.
2. Data on air quality allows us to assess if a certain location is satisfying the CPCB, WHO, or OSHA air quality guidelines.
3. We would mainly be able to identify polluted locations, the amount of pollution, and the level of air quality with the use of data gathered from air quality monitoring.
4. Monitoring the quality of the air would help assess the effectiveness of localized air pollution management initiatives.
5. We can better comprehend the death rate from air pollution in any given location by using statistics on air quality. The short- and long-term illnesses and disorders brought on by air pollution can also be evaluated and contrasted.
6. Control measures for the preservation of the environment and the wellbeing of all living things can be developed based on the data gathered [19].

IV. THE DISADVANTAGES OF USING A MONITORING SYSTEM FOR AIR QUALITY

1. The air is not cleaned by an air quality sensor.
2. The source of the contaminants is not displayed.
3. A consumer-grade monitor typically costs \$150.
4. Carbon monoxide (CO) is not typically measured by air quality devices.
5. Both dangerous and safe substances are included in the measured VOCs.
6. It can take up to seven days for air quality monitors to calibrate [21].

V. INSTRUMENTS FOR ASSESSING THE QUALITY OF THE AIR

1. Photoionization Detectors (PIDs)

PIDs are the most widely utilized on-site volatiles parts-per-million (ppm) detection equipment. Because volatiles from petroleum products or chemical usage make many environmental sites dangerous, the PID is essential for supplying equipment that will function well there. The most popular use for PIDs is the detection of volatile organic compounds (VOCs).
2. Wireless Gas Detection Systems

Standard and custom wireless technologies are used by wireless systems for air monitoring for chemical and compound detection to provide dependable "always on" cable-free connectivity enabling quick, simple, and adaptable deployments. Wireless solutions combine battery-powered sensors with integrated radio-frequency (RF) technology running on license-free frequency bands to deliver proven long-term results, even in the most challenging environments.
3. Single Gas Monitors and Tubes

Toxic gas sensors in single gas monitors employ polarographic cells or electrochemical (voltametric) sensors to provide continuous analysis. During operation, sample gas travels through a diffusion medium before being absorbed by an electrocatalytic sensor electrode. An electric current produced by an electrochemical reaction is directly proportional to the concentration of the gas.

4. Flame Ionization Detectors (FID)

These devices ionize airborne pollutants using a flame. They can be found and measured once they have ionized. A hydrogen flame is used by FIDs as a method in order to ionize organic vapor. Almost all organic molecules, including those containing carbon-hydrogen or carbon-carbon bonds, are recognized by FIDs as being reactive. Inorganic substances will not cause a reaction from FIDs. The sample is subjected to a hydrogen flame inside the detection chamber, which ionizes the organic vapors.

5. High Vacuum Air Samplers

These devices ionize airborne pollutants using a flame. They can be found and measured once they have ionized. A hydrogen flame is used by FIDs as a method in order to ionize organic vapor. Almost all organic molecules, including those containing carbon-hydrogen or carbon-carbon bonds, are recognized by FIDs as being reactive. Inorganic substances will not cause a reaction from FIDs. The sample is subjected to a hydrogen flame inside the detection chamber, which ionizes the organic vapors [22].

CONCLUSION

We've reviewed several research on air quality, noted advancements in the field of technology, and spoken about some significant advantages of air quality monitoring systems [20]. The disadvantages of a monitoring and control system are also covered in detail [23]. Also covered are the instruments used to measure the quality of the air.

REFERENCES

1. Saad, H. et al., "Deep learning based multimodal urban air quality prediction and trafca analytics", Scientific Reports, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-49296-7>.
2. Ambient air pollution: a global assessment of exposure and burden of disease. (2016). World Health Organization. – 121. (available on the <https://www.who.int/phe/publications/air-pollution-global-assessment/en/>).
3. Zou, B., Luo, Y., Wan, N., Zheng, ZH., Sternberg, T., Liao, Y. "Performance comparison of LUR and OK in PM2.5 concentration mapping: a multidimensional perspective", Scientific Reports, 2015, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep08698>.
4. Anenberg, S., Schwartz, J., Shindell, D., Amann, M., Faluvegi, G., Klimont, Z., Janssens-Maenhout, G., Pozzoli, L., Van Dingenen, R., Vignati, E., Emberson, L., Muller, N., West, J., Williams, M., Demkine, V., Hicks, W.K., Kuylenstierna, J., Raes, F., Ramanathan, V., "Global air quality and health co-benefits of mitigating near-term climate change through methane and black carbon emission control", Environmental Health Perspectives, 120, 2012.
5. Kaiser, J., "How dirty air hurts the heart", Science, Vol. 307, Pp. 1858-1859, 2015.
6. Wang, S., H., Hung, R., Y., Lin, N., H., Gómez-Losada, Á., Pires, J., Shimada, K., Hatakeyama, S., Takami, A., "Estimation of background PM2.5 concentrations for an air-polluted environment. Atmospheric Research, Vol. 231, 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosres.2019.104636>.
7. Karan, A., Ali, K., Teelucksingh, S., Sakhamuri S., "The impact of air pollution on the incidence and mortality of COVID-19", Global Health Research and Policy, Vol. 5, No. 39, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41256-020-00167-y>.
8. Comunian, S., Dongo, D., Milani, Ch., Palestin, P., "Air pollution and COVID-19: the role of particulate matter in the spread and increase of COVID-19's morbidity and mortality", International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health, Vol. 17, No. 12, Pp. 4487, 2020, <https://dx.doi.org/10.3390%2Fijerph17124487>.
9. Zoran, M.A., Savastru, R.S., Savastru, D.M., Tautan, M.N. "Assessing the relationship between surface levels of PM2.5 and PM10 particulate matter impact on COVID-19 in Milan, Italy", Science of the Total Environment, Vol. 738. 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139825>.
10. Rodriguez-Urrego, D., Rodriguez-Urrego, L., "Air quality during the COVID-19: PM2.5 analysis in the 50 most polluted capital cities in the world", Environmental Pollution, Vol. 266, No. 1, Pp. 115042, 2020, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2020.115042>.
11. World Bank. Ukraine Country Environmental Analysis. (2016). World Bank, Washington, DC. Retrieved from: <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/handle/10986/24971>.
12. Prokhorova, S., "An approach to using the AQI components in urban air pollution sources identifying" Visnyk of V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University, series "Geology. Geography. Ecology", Vol. 59, Pp. 209-220, 2023, <https://doi.org/10.26565/2410-7360-2023-59-15>.
13. Thalman, R., "Development and Testing of a Rocket-Based Sensor for Atmospheric Sensing Using an Unmanned Aerial System", Sensors Vol. 24, Pp. 1768, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24061768>.
14. Hakon, M., et al., "Use of a Distributed Micro-sensor System for Monitoring the Indoor Particulate Matter Concentration in the Atmosphere of Ferroalloy Production Plants", Pp. 1-11, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-022-05487-7>.
15. Samad, A., Kieser, J., Chourdakis, I., Vogt, U., "Developing a Cloud-Based Air Quality Monitoring Platform Using Low-Cost Sensors", Sensors, 2024, 24, 945. <https://doi.org/10.3390/s24030945>.
16. Utbah, R., et al., "Evaluations of Low-cost Air Quality Sensors for Particulate Matter (PM2.5) under Indoor and Outdoor Conditions", Sensors and Materials, Vol. 35, No. 8, Pp. 2881–2895, 2023.

17. Zanic, N., Spalevic, V., Bulatovic, N., Pavlicevic, N., Dudic, B., “Measurement of Air Pollution Parameters in Montenegro Using the Ecomar System”, *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 18, 6565. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18126565>.
18. Samad, A., Melchor Mimiaga, F.E., Laquai, B., Vogt, U., “Investigating a Low-Cost Dryer Designed for Low-Cost PM Sensors Measuring Ambient Air Quality”, *Sensors*, 21, 804. 2021, <https://doi.org/10.3390/s21030804>.
19. <https://www.ppsthane.com/blog/benefits-of-air-quality-monitoring>.
20. Musa DA. M, Ahmad M. A, Munirah A. S, Danladi K. G, Mukhtar I. B, & Muhammad A. B., “A System for Monitoring Air Quality has Several Important Benefits”, In *Global Journal of Research in Engineering & Computer Sciences* (Vol. 4, Number 2, pp. 152–155), 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11078034>.
21. https://ecolivingexpert.com/air-quality-monitors-pros-and-cons/#google_vignette.
22. https://www.geotechenv.com/air_quality_instruments.html#:~:text=Aerosol%20photometers%20operate%20by%20detecting,smokes%2C%20mists%2C%20and%20fumes.
23. Abdullahi M.G, & Muhammad A. B. “The Disadvantages of using a Monitoring System for Air Quality” In *Global Journal of Research in Engineering & Computer Sciences*, Vol. 4, Number 3, pp. 27–30, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11246718>.